

Studying the Physiological Response to Adding Different Concentrations of Certain Nano-Amino Acids to the Drinking Water of Broiler

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Article History:

Received: 03.11.2025 Revised: 12.12.2025 Accepted: 15.12.2025 Published: 19.12.2025

Abstract

The study aimed to investigate the effect of some zinc-loaded nano-amino acids (methionine Met, lysine Lys) on the physiological characteristics of ROSS 380 broiler chickens for 35 days. The experiment was conducted in the fields of the College of Agriculture, Al-Qasim Green University. 450 birds were used, divided into five treatments, and each treatment had six replicates (90 birds per treatment and 15 birds per replicate). The experimental treatments were: T1 was a control treatment without addition, T2 was an addition of (methionine at a concentration of 2.5% and a dose of 1 ml/1 liter), T3 was an addition of (methionine at a concentration of 3.5% and a dose of 1 ml/1 liter), T4 was an addition of (lysine at a concentration of 2% and a dose of 1 ml/1 liter), and T5 was an addition of (lysine at a concentration of 3% and a dose of 1 ml/1 liter). The results of the experiment were as follows: Treatment T4 showed a significant advantage ($P \leq 0.05$) in total protein and albumin concentrations. No significant difference was observed between the treatments in globulin concentration. Cholesterol, triglycerides, VLDL, LDL, and MDA concentrations were significantly higher in treatment T1 compared to treatments T4 and T5. HDL concentration was also significantly higher ($P \leq 0.01$) in treatments T3, T4, and T5 compared to treatments T1 and T2. All treatments with amino acid supplementation showed a significant improvement ($P \leq 0.01$) in IgA and IgG concentrations compared to the control. Treatments T3, T4, and T5 showed a significant increase ($P \leq 0.01$) in SOD and GSH enzyme concentrations. Creatinine concentration was significantly higher ($P \leq 0.05$) in treatment T1 compared to treatments T4 and T5. No significant difference was observed in urea concentration between the treatments.

Keywords: Nanoamino acids, Methionine, Lysine, Broiler meat, Antioxidants.

Suggested citation: Hassoon, M.H., Ajafar, M.H., & Al-Jaryan, I.L. (2025). Studying the Physiological Response to Adding Different Concentrations of Certain Nano-Amino Acids to the Drinking Water of Broiler. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 4(1), 3-11. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2026.4\(1\).01](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2026.4(1).01)

Introduction

The poultry industry is considered one of the most efficient branches of animal production in providing food security for a large number of the

world's population. With the use of intensive breeding techniques, global production of poultry products is constantly increasing (Grzinic et al., 2023). During manufacturing, feed materials are subjected to heat treatment,

which can lead to a deficiency or damage in some amino acids, especially the essential ones (Arkan et al., 2025a). A deficiency in dietary amino acids affects the quantity and proportion of tissue produced by the chick. These effects vary depending on the type of amino acid (Tasaki et al., 1972; Okumura and Mori, 1979) and the severity of the deficiency (Kubena et al., 1972; Velu et al., 1972; Boomgaardt and Baker, 1973; Sugahara et al., 1984). This negatively impacts the productive and physiological performance and the antioxidant system of the raised birds (Arkan et al., 2023). (2025 b), Methionine is one of the essential amino acids important for birds. It is a sulfur amino acid and is classified as a neutral amino acid (i.e., methionine contains one amino group in the formula (NH₃) and one carboxyl group in the formula (COO⁻). It is an aliphatic amino acid. L-Methionine represents the natural form of methionine, while the isomer mixture of DL-Methionine and its predecessor DL (HMTBA) 2-hydroxy-(4-methylthion)butanoic acid represents the two synthetic sources added to poultry feed (Goodson et al., 2012). Methionine has also been found to play a role in protecting cell membranes from oxidative damage because it participates in the synthesis of the enzyme glutathione peroxidase, in addition to its work with the thiorodoxin compound in directly eliminating reactive oxygen species (ROS). (Levine et al., 2000). Lysine is one of the important amino acids in common broiler diets. The ratio of lysine to all other essential amino acids is of great importance for optimal broiler performance (Corzo et al., 2002). Increasing lysine levels in the diet has been found to increase carcass protein levels (Sibbald and Wolynetz, 1986). Lysine requirements for broilers are higher in low-protein diets to maximize weight gain and feeding efficiency (Labadan et al., 2001), even at normal crude protein (CP) levels. High lysine content increases the growth rate in broilers (Holsheimer and Veerkamp, 1992). Lysine has

also been found to directly affect carcass quality and breast meat size (Schutte and Pack, 1995) and reduces excess fat deposition in the carcass by regulating the body fat profile (Moran and Bilgili, 1990). (and others, 2004). Therefore, the current study aims to investigate the effect of adding methionine and lysine to drinking water on the physiological and immune performance of chickens.

Methods

This experiment was conducted at the poultry farms of the College of Agriculture in Babylon Governorate from February 10, 2025 to March 15, 2025. The experiment used 450 unsexed Ross 308 broiler chicks prepared from the light hatchery. These were randomly distributed into 30 (cans) with 5 experimental treatments of 90 birds each. Each treatment included 6 replicates of 15 birds each. Feeding rations were used according to the Ross 308 2022 production guide (starter ration from 1-11 days old, grower ration from 12-24 days old, and finisher ration from 25-35 days old), as shown in Table 1. The experimental treatments were as follows: Treatment 1: Control group with no additives; Treatment 2: Addition of 1 ml/L of methionine nano-amino acid at a concentration of 2.5%; Treatment 3: Addition of 1 ml/L of methionine nano-amino acid at a concentration of 3.5%; Treatment 4: Addition of 1 ml/L of lysine nano-amino acid at a concentration of 2%; Treatment 5: Addition of 1 ml/L of lysine nano-amino acid at a concentration of 3%. The amount of dissolved zinc: Zinc acetate dihydrate: 11 g was dissolved in 500 ml of distilled water to obtain a concentration of 0.1 M, forming a clear, colorless solution. A small amount of acetic acid was added to increase its solubility. The test was performed using FTIR and aqueous XRD. Amino acids were converted into zinc-loaded nanomaterials according to Subramanian and Al Ghaferi (2013).

Table 1. Shows the Feed Ingredients Included in the Ration along with Their Calculated Chemical Composition

Item / Nutrient	Starter % (1–11 d)	Grower % (12–24 d)	Finisher % (25–42 d)
Feed Ingredients			
Yellow corn	43.00	49.00	50.00

Soybean meal (48% protein)	32.00	27.50	23.00
Wheat	16.00	13.00	16.20
Protein concentrate	5.00	5.00	5.00
Vegetable oil	2.00	3.50	3.75
Limestone	1.25	1.30	1.10
Dicalcium phosphate	0.60	0.50	0.60
L-lysine	0.15	0.10	0.06
Salt	0.00	0.10	0.29
Total	100	100	100
Calculated Composition based on NRC 1994			
Crude protein %	22.90	20.90	19.20
Metabolizable energy (kcal/kg)	3006.00	3138.45	3184.49
Methionine %	0.5008	0.47695	0.4534
Lysine %	1.42	1.2502	1.10
Methionine + Cystine %	0.87	0.82	0.74464
Calcium %	0.932	0.95	0.8522
Available phosphorus %	0.47	0.4406	0.45366

Note: *Protein Concentrate Type Brocon-5 Special W: Origin of China. Each kg contains: 40% Crude Protein, 3.5% Fat, 1% Fiber, 6% Calcium, 3% Available Phosphorus, 3.25% Lysine, 3.90% Methionine + Cysteine, 2.2% Sodium, 2100 kcal/kg Metabolic Energy, 20000 IU Vitamin A, 40000 IU Vitamin D3, 500 mg Vitamin E, 30 mg Vitamin K3, 15 mg Vitamin B1 + B2, 150 mg Vitamin B3, 20 mg Vitamin B6, 300 mg Vitamin B12, 10 mg Folic Acid, 100 mcg Biotin, 1 mg Iron, 100 mg Copper, 1.2 1 mg manganese, 800 mg zinc, 15 mg iodine, 2 mg selenium, 6 mg cobalt, 900 mg antioxidant (BHT); **Chemical analysis of the feed was calculated according to FEED STUFF (2016).

Traits studied: Glucose, cholesterol, and ALT/AST enzyme concentrations were determined in the blood serum of birds at 35 days of age. This was achieved by separating the serum from the blood using a centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. The aforementioned traits were then measured in a laboratory in Babylon Governorate. Glucose concentration was determined using a Roche (Germany) measuring kit according to the Coles (1986) method, and cholesterol concentration was determined using a Roche (Germany) measuring kit according to the Franey and Elias (1968) method. The concentrations of ALT and AST enzymes were determined using a Roche kit according to the method of Ritman and Frankel (1957). Glutathione peroxidase was measured according to the method of Hafemann et al. (1974), and malondialdehyde concentration was determined using a Roche kit based on the method of Buege and Aust (1978). Uric acid concentration in bird blood serum was determined by enzymatic hydrolysis according to the method of Henry et al. (1982). Triglyceride levels were measured using a Roche kit according to the method of Fossati and Prencipe (1982). HDL levels were measured using a Roche kit according to the

method of Tietz (1986). LDL levels were determined according to the method of Martia et al. (1997). VLDL levels were estimated using the method of Friedewald et al. (1972). Globulin levels were estimated using the method of Bishop et al. (2000). Immunoglobulin concentrations were estimated following the steps described by Synder et al. (1984).

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using a completely randomized design (CRD) to study the effect of the treatments on the different traits. Significant differences between means were compared using Duncan's (1955) multiple-choice test. The SAS software (2012) was used for statistical analysis according to the following mathematical model:

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + T_i + e_{ij} \quad (1)$$

where: Y_{ij} : observation value j for treatment i .

μ : overall mean for the trait.

T_i: effect of treatment i (the study included the effect of the five treatments mentioned above).

e_{ij}: normally distributed random error with a mean of zero and a variance of 2 e₆.

Results and Discussion

Table (2-4) shows the effect of the study on some biochemical characteristics. A significant advantage ($P \leq 0.05$) was observed for treatment T4 in the concentration of total protein and albumin compared to the control treatment. No significant difference was observed between the study treatments in the concentration of globulin. However, the concentration of cholesterol, triglycerides, VLDL, LDL, and MDA increased significantly in treatment T1

compared to treatments T4 and T5. The concentration of HDL also increased significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) in treatments T3, T4, and T5 compared to treatments T1 and T2. At the immunological level, all treatments with the addition of amino acids improved significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) compared to the control treatment through the increase in the concentration of IgA and IgG in them. Treatments T3, T4, and T5 showed significantly higher ($P \leq 0.01$) SOD and GSH enzyme concentrations compared to the control treatment. Creatinine concentration was significantly higher ($P \leq 0.05$) in treatment T1 compared to treatments T4 and T5. No significant difference was observed in urea concentration among the treatment treatments.

Table 2. Effect of Different Treatments on Studied Protein Profile

Traits	Treatments					Significant t
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	
Total protein (g/dl)	0.24± 3.86b	0.42± 4.14ab	0.23± 4.31ab	0.03± 4.89a	0.26± 4.57ab	*
Albumin (g/dl)	0.06± 2.21b	0.05± 2.44ab	0.06± 2.43ab	0.13± 2.69a	0.08± 2.36b	*
Globulin (g/dl)	0.23± 1.64	0.37± 1.70	0.25± 1.88	0.09± 2.20	0.20± 2.21	N.S

Note: Means with different letters within the same row differ significantly from one another. * ($P \leq 0.05$), ** ($P \leq 0.01$), N/A. Not significant.

Table 3. Effect of Different Treatments on Studied Lipid Profile

Traits	Treatments					Significant
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	
Cholesterol (mg/dl)	12.40± 214.90a	21.83± 178.91ab	3.71± 181.27ab	4.83± 174.79b	2.91± 175.44b	*
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	17.69± 149.51a	2.27± 108.42b	6.38± 111.36b	8.22± 111.10b	11.08± 115.70b	*
HDL (mg/dl)	2.41± 60.53c	3.84± 78.97b	2.72± 93.06a	2.68± 94.28a	4.22± 91.38a	**
LDL (g/dl)	14.34± 124.47a	18.50± 78.26b	4.95± 65.93b	1.68± 58.29b	8.35± 60.92b	**
VLDL (mg/d)	3.53± 29.90a	0.45± 21.68b	1.28± 22.27b	1.64± 22.21b	2.22± 23.14b	*

Note: Means with different letters within the same row differ significantly from one another. * ($P \leq 0.05$), ** ($P \leq 0.01$), N/A. Not significant.

Table 4. Effect of Different Treatments on Studied Antioxidants Parameters

Traits	Treatments					Significant
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	
MDA (mg/dl)	25.84± 245.27a	8.37± 187.68b	3.05± 179.01b	14.89± 168.69b	2.47± 164.24b	**
SOD (mg/dl)	5.89± 136.95c	8.04± 152.55bc	6.67± 166.45ab	5.26± 173.91a	3.10± 177.94a	**
GSH (mg/dl)	2.74± 322.44c	21.62± 417.64b	4.67± 457.64a	3.13± 490.11a	8.55± 486.51a	**

Creatinine (mg/dl)	0.21± 1.20a	0.24± 1.03ab	0.06± 0.700ab	0.12± 0.667b	0.03± 0.733a	*
Urea (mg/dl)	0.29± 4.81	0.12± 4.32	0.15± 4.33	0.50± 4.05	0.28± 3.96	N.S

Note: Means with different letters within the same row differ significantly from one another. *($P \leq 0.05$), ** ($P \leq 0.01$), N/A. Not significant.

Table (5) shows the effect of treatments in some immunity indicators, significantly higher ($P \leq 0.01$) for T4 and T5 in IgG and IgA, while

significantly higher ($P \leq 0.01$) for T3 treatment in ND and IB titer compared to T1 treatment.

Table 5. Effect of Different Treatments on Studied Immune Parameters

Treatments	Traits				
	IgG (mg/mL)	IgA (mg/mL)	ND titer	AI titer	IB titer
T1	15.55± 175.08c	3.24± 77.04c	0.26± 3.82c	1.73± 4.53	0.71± 15.14b
T2	3.94± 291.17b	4.75± 94.90bc	0.25± 4.57bc	0.29± 4.92	2.61± 16.89ab
T3	4.52± 290.18b	9.45± 103.38b	0.39± 7.03a	2.47± 8.46	3.36± 24.89a
T4	15.2± 347.46a	4.26± 151.17a	1.26± 4.06bc	0.61± 5.30	3.08± 19.47ab
T5	14.32± 360.78a	5.50± 149.57a	0.31± 5.91ab	0.37± 6.26	2.23± 22.05ab
Significant	**	**	**	N.S	*

Note: Means with different letters within the same row differ significantly from one another. *($P \leq 0.05$), ** ($P \leq 0.01$), N/A. Not significant.

The improvement in total protein, albumin, and immunoglobulin levels may be attributed to methionine. Methionine is the first limiting amino acid in poultry diets and is involved in the formation of enzymes, albumin, and immunoglobulins. Increased availability of methionine improves protein synthesis in the liver and immune tissues, leading to higher serum total protein concentrations. Methionine is also converted to S-adenosylmethionine (SAM), a methyl donor in several biochemical reactions that regulate immune gene expression. This promotes the production of immunoglobulins (IgG, IgM, IgA) by B lymphocytes (Handique et al., 2019; Cengiz et al., 2008; Arkan et al., 2025a). Alternatively, the improvement may be due to lysine, which is essential for muscle and plasma protein synthesis, thus increasing serum total protein levels and activating insulin-like growth factor. (IGF-1) increases the synthesis of liver proteins, and lysine plays a role in lymphocyte proliferation and antibody formation, leading to elevated serum immunoglobulins (Lee et al., 2020; Mousa et al., 2023). The improvement in antioxidant levels (SOD and GSH enzymes) may be attributed to the role of lysine and

methionine, as they are directly or indirectly involved in the synthesis of glutathione (GSH) and SOD, thus improving their blood levels (Mousa et al., 2023; Arkan et al., 2025a and b).

Furthermore, the improved lipid profile in methionine supplementation treatments primarily reduces MDA because it is a source of antioxidant compounds (such as glutathione) and a methyl group donor (SAM) that enhances lipid metabolism (Miao et al., 2021). Lysine contributes to L-carnitine synthesis, with methionine as the methyl group donor, which promotes the transport of fatty acids into the mitochondria for β -oxidation and reduces triglyceride accumulation (Mirzaei et al., 2022). The combination of these two amino acids can reduce lipid peroxidation (MDA) and lower triglyceride and cholesterol levels in broiler chickens (Abd El-Wahab et al., 2015). Methionine is converted to S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) and then partially converted to cysteine, which is involved in glutathione (GSH) synthesis. Glutathione is a major cellular antioxidant that protects against free radical formation and reduces lipid peroxidation. Therefore, MDA levels decrease. Studies in broiler chickens have shown that

methionine supplementation improves antioxidant markers SOD, GPx, and GSH, and reduces MDA (Kachungwa et al., 2022). Lysine is the primary compound converted to trimethyllysine, the initial step in L-carnitine synthesis. However, the methylation process requires SAM, i.e., methionine. Therefore, lysine and methionine together support carnitine synthesis. Carnitine transports long-chain fatty acids to the mitochondria for β -oxidation, thus reducing lipid levels and fat accumulation in body tissues (Mirzaei et al., 2021).

Conclusions

1. The study showed that adding zinc-loaded methionine and lysine nanoparticles to the drinking water of broiler chickens resulted in a significant improvement in physiological and immunological indicators compared to the control treatment.
2. The 2% lysine treatment (T4) was superior in raising total protein and serum albumin levels.
3. No significant differences were observed between the treatments in total globulin concentration, but the added treatments improved immunoglobulins IgA and IgG.
4. The T4 and T5 treatments showed a significant decrease in cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL, and VLDL, with an increase in HDL, reflecting an improved lipid profile due to the stimulation of fatty acid oxidation and reduced accumulation.
5. MDA levels decreased, and SOD and GSH enzyme activity increased in the treatments with added amino acids, indicating improved antioxidant capacity and reduced oxidative stress in the birds.
6. A significant increase in creatinine concentration was observed in the control treatment compared to the supplementation treatments, indicating that nano-methionine and nano-lysine contribute to supporting liver and kidney function.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended to add nano-methionine at a concentration of 3.5% or nano-lysine at a concentration of 2–3% to the drinking water of broiler chickens to improve physiological and immune performance.

2. This supplementation can be adopted as a natural and safe alternative to reduce oxidative stress and improve meat quality in intensive rearing systems.

3. The use of amino acid nanoparticles is preferable due to their increased solubility, absorption, and biological activity.

4. Further studies are recommended to determine the optimal dosage and the cumulative effect of these compounds on cellular immunity and liver enzyme activity.

5. It is recommended to expand the experiments to include different broiler breeds and various rearing conditions (such as heat stress) to confirm the consistency of the results.
6. This approach can be used to improve vaccine response and reduce the need for antibiotics in the poultry industry.

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